

A Fast Method for Measuring Vibrotactile Threshold Profiles Across Frequency

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Abstract. Measuring vibrotactile detection thresholds across frequency is time-consuming because conventional procedures require separate adaptive measurements at each tested frequency. This limitation becomes critical when dense spectral sampling or multiple body locations are needed. Inspired by Békésy audiometry, we developed a rapid tactile screening method in which vibration frequency is swept across a broad range while stimulus level is adjusted from the participant’s ongoing responses. In a pilot study with 12 participants, sinusoidal vibrations were delivered with a calibrated handheld piezoelectric stimulator, and threshold tracking was obtained over 40 logarithmically spaced frequencies between 20 and 1000 Hz in less than two minutes. The method recovered the expected main features of vibrotactile sensitivity, including highest fingertip sensitivity around 200–300 Hz, while remaining much faster than conventional point-by-point procedures, which required about 30 minutes. Measurements at the fingertip, wrist, forearm, and lips also revealed distinct threshold profiles across body sites. These preliminary results suggest that sweep-based threshold tracking can provide a practical tool for rapid vibrotactile screening and for future studies of anatomical or clinical differences in tactile sensitivity.

Keywords: Vibrotactile threshold · Békésy tracking · Frequency sweep.

1 Introduction

Measuring vibrotactile threshold as a function of frequency usually requires a separate adaptive procedure at each tested frequency. This makes dense sampling slow, especially when several body locations must be assessed. Yet dense sampling may be necessary because the shape of the tactile threshold profile cannot be assumed *a priori*.

A similar problem was addressed in audiology with Békésy audiometry, where frequency is swept continuously while stimulus amplitude level is adjusted from the participant’s ongoing response [1]. The method relies on the assumption that threshold varies gradually across neighboring frequencies, allowing the profile to be tracked rather than measured point by point.

Here we adapt this principle to vibrotactile stimulation. The goal is not to replace long psychophysical measurements when maximum precision is required,

but to provide a fast screening method able to capture the main shape of the tactile sensitivity curve across frequency and body location.

Fig. 1. Mean vibrotactile detection thresholds as a function of frequency for four body sites measured with the rapid screening procedure: wrist, finger, lips, and forearm. Thresholds are expressed in peak to peak displacement in dB re $1 \mu\text{m}$. The blue curve shows a previously published average fingertip reference dataset (mean \pm 1 SE) [3]. The rapid method captures the expected minimum threshold for the finger around 200-300 Hz and reveals distinct sensitivity profiles across anatomical locations.

2 Method

A pilot study was conducted with 12 participants. Vibrotactile stimulation was delivered using a calibrated handheld piezoelectric stimulator (Physik Instrumente P-841, E509 controller, E504 amplifier), controlled by a custom Python script. Sinusoidal vibrations were generated at a sampling rate of 8 kHz and tested at 40 logarithmically spaced frequencies between 20 and 1000 Hz.

Each stimulus lasted 1.1 s and consisted of 100 ms silence, a 200 ms raised-cosine onset ramp, a 500 ms steady segment, a 200 ms offset ramp, and 100 ms silence. Level, defined as peak to peak displacement, was adjusted in 5 dB steps. Participants were instructed to press a response button whenever they felt the vibration. Detection of the stimulus led to a 5 dB decrease for the next presentation, while non-detection led to a 5 dB increase. The level estimated at one frequency was used to initialize the next frequency, so that tracking could follow the expected local continuity of the threshold curve.

To initialize the procedure near threshold, stimulation started at a frequency of 150 Hz and the level was progressively reduced until the participant no longer detected the vibration; the level was then increased by one step before the sweep began. The full measurement required less than two minutes. For comparison, a conventional frequency-by-frequency threshold measurement required about 30 minutes. Threshold curves were collected at several body sites, including the fingertip, hairless skin of the wrist and the upper forearm, and lips. To eliminate any potential auditory cues from the tactile stimuli, participants wore sound-attenuating headphones that played a masking white noise.

3 Results

The proposed procedure rapidly recovered plausible vibrotactile threshold profiles over a broad frequency range in less than 2 minutes, compared with about 30 minutes for the longer reference procedure. As shown in Fig. 1, the fingertip exhibited the expected region of highest sensitivity around 200–300 Hz, with a minimum near 240 Hz at about $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ ($-5 \text{ dB re } 1 \mu\text{m}$). The sweep-based method may lead to threshold estimates that differ by about 10–15 dB from those obtained with the longer reference procedure using the same equipment [3], but it preserved the overall shape of the threshold curve and its main physiological features. The measurements also distinguished body sites. The fingertip showed the lowest thresholds and the clearest sensitivity peak in the Pacinian range. The forearm and wrist showed higher thresholds overall, whereas the lips displayed a flatter profile in the 200–300 Hz region. These differences are consistent with known anatomical variation in receptor density and receptor type across the body [2]. Overall, these pilot results indicate that a Békésy-inspired sweep procedure can provide a fast estimate of vibrotactile sensitivity across frequency, while preserving the main physiological features of the threshold profile despite a moderate loss in absolute precision.

Acknowledgments. The study was funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (310030, 215062) and the Bertarelli Catalyst Fund.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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